

Kinetics and Mechanism of the Aqueous Polymerization of Methacrylonitrile and Acrylonitrile initiated by Potassium Persulphate at 50° in an Inert Atmosphere of Nitrogen Gas

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The kinetics and mechanism of the aqueous polymerization of methacrylonitrile (MAN) and acrylonitrile (AN) have been investigated experimentally within the solubility range of monomers at 50° in an unbuffered aqueous medium and in an inert atmosphere of nitrogen gas. The rates of polymerizations under various conditions have been followed by the conventional gravimetric method. The molecular weights of the polymers have been estimated from the intrinsic viscosity data and also by the gel permeation chromatographic method as a function of monomer and initiator, potassium persulphate (KPS) concentrations. It has been found that the rates of polymerization (R_p) are given by

$$R_p \propto [\text{MAN}]^{1.60 \pm 0.05} [\text{KPS}]^{0.50 \pm 0.05}$$

and

$$R_p \propto [\text{AN}]^{1.46 \pm 0.04} [\text{KPS}]^{0.46 \pm 0.04}$$

Both in the MAN-KPS and AN-KPS systems, the injection of initiator late in a run increases the rate of aqueous polymerization but has no measurable effect on the viscosity average molecular weight (\bar{M}_v) of the polymers, whereas the addition of extra amount of monomer late in a run increases both the rates of polymerization and the \bar{M}_v . The rate of the aqueous polymerization is higher in the AN-KPS system than that in MAN-KPS system. The particle size distribution has been measured. A mechanism has been suggested to explain the kinetic data.

We studied earlier the mode of persulphate decomposition in presence of methacrylonitrile monomer¹ and acrylonitrile monomer², and found that the kinetic data could be explained quantitatively by the following elementary reactions :

where M is the monomer molecule and $(\text{M}_j^{\cdot})_w$ is a water-soluble monomeric/oligomeric free radical. k_5 and k_{10} were found as 1.70×10^{-5} and $5.08 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for the acrylonitrile monomer² respectively at 50°, whereas the counterpart rate constants for the methacrylonitrile

monomer¹ were found as 1.05×10^{-5} and $1.14 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively. In light of this finding, we have investigated the persulphate initiated aqueous polymerizations of methacrylonitrile and acrylonitrile. These two monomers differ from the common vinyl monomers, namely, styrene, vinyl acetate, methylacrylate, in the respect that MAN and AN are non-solvents for the corresponding polymers. This also led us to study the kinetics in detail.

Results and Discussion

The aqueous polymerization of MAN and AN have been studied in the initiator concentration range $(0.5-7.5) \times 10^{-3}$, MAN concentration $(0.16-0.30)$ and AN concentration $(0.20-0.45) \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

Repeating a run ten times, we have found that both the rates of polymerizations and the viscosity average molecular weights are highly reproducible within $\pm 5\%$.

The yield-time curves are shown in Figs. 1 and 2. Fig. 1 shows the results at a given

Fig. 1. The conversion-time curves of methacrylonitrile (MAN) polymerization at 50° in aqueous solution; recipe $[\text{MAN}] = 0.24 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $[\text{KPS}]$ varies; (A) 1.0×10^{-3} , (B) 2.0×10^{-3} , (C) 5.0×10^{-3} , (D) $7.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; ionic strength kept constant by adding K_2SO_4

Fig. 2. The conversion-time curves of acrylonitrile (AN) polymerization at 50° in aqueous solution; recipe $[\text{KPS}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $[\text{AN}]$ varies; (A) 0.20, (B) 0.25, (C) 0.30 and (D) 0.45 mol dm^{-3} .

concentration of the monomer ($\text{MAN} = 0.24 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) and at various initiator concentrations (1.0×10^{-3} to $7.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$). The ionic strength ($\mu = 22.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) was kept constant by adding K_2SO_4 . Fig. 2 shows the results at a given concentrations of initiator ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) and at various monomer concentrations ($[\text{AN}] = 0.20\text{--}0.45 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$). The rates of polymerizations are found to increase with the increase of monomer and initiator concentrations.

The initial rate of polymerization has been determined empirically by plotting percent yield/time versus time and extrapolating the resulting curves to zero time. For such plots, the conversion generally remained below 20% conversion. Some such plots are shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Estimation of rate of polymerization at zero time, $(R_p)_{t=0}$ or zero conversion from the intercept of the plot, time average rate (i.e. % conversion at time t /time t) versus time t at the early stages of the reaction; recipe $[\text{MAN}] = 0.24 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $[\text{KPS}]$ varies: (A) 1.0×10^{-3} , (B) 2.0×10^{-3} , (C) 5.0×10^{-3} , (D) $7.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

When the initiator concentration and monomer concentrations are high, the rate of polymerization of AN has been found to be very high and so the initial rate of polymerization could not be estimated accurately. The conventional order plots are shown in Fig. 4 and the results are summarised in Table 1.

Fig. 4. Order plot for the initiator (I) from the rates of polymerization : (A, \blacktriangle) rate defined as [6% conversion/time] for a given concentration of MAN (0.20 mol dm^{-3}); (B, \triangle) rate defined as [6% conversion/time] and (C, O) rate defined as [12% conversion/time] for a given concentration of AN (0.30 mol dm^{-3}).

TABLE 1

Monomer	Initiator exponent (reaction order)	Monomer exponent (reaction order)	Conversion %
AN	0.52 ± 0.06	1.54 ± 0.02	0
AN	0.48 ± 0.02	1.56 ± 0.08	6
AN	0.46 ± 0.02	1.48 ± 0.06	12
AN	0.46 ± 0.03	1.40 ± 0.05	8-12
MAN	0.56 ± 0.04	1.60 ± 0.80	0
MAN	0.46 ± 0.02	1.54 ± 0.01	6
MAN	0.46 ± 0.02	1.50 ± 0.04	12
MAN	0.53 ± 0.02	1.60 ± 0.02	8-12

The relation between the viscosity average molecular weight \bar{M}_v and the initiator concentration is shown in Fig. 5. It is evident that at low conversion (below 20%) a relation exists,

$$\log \bar{M}_v = \log A - \log [I]^x$$

where A and x are the constants, and $[I]$ denotes

Fig. 5. Variation of viscosity average molecular weight with the initiator concentrations (KPS) at 10% conversion; recipe $[MAN] = 0.30 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ at varying $[KPS]$.

initiator concentration; the value of x is found to be 0.50 ± 0.06 .

Fig. 6 shows the empirical correlation between the viscosity-average molecular weight and the

Fig. 6. \bar{M}_v as a function of conversion and also the time average rate as a function of conversion; recipe $[MAN] = 0.30 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $[KPS] = 5.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$: (\triangle) molecular weight, (\blacktriangle) time average rate; recipe $[MAN] = 0.30 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $[KPS] = 7.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$: (o) time average rate, (\bullet) molecular weight.

TABLE 2—COMPARISON OF METHACRYLONITRILE AND ACRYLONITRILE DURING THE AQUEOUS POLYMERIZATION

$[KPS] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[MAN] = [AN] = 0.30 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

Time min	Methacrylonitrile			Acrylonitrile		
	Conversion %	C.S. (mmol MgSO ₄)	$[\eta] \times 10^{-2}$ dm ³ g ⁻¹	Conversion %	C.S. (mmol MgSO ₄)	$[\eta] \times 10^{-2}$ dm ³ g ⁻¹
60	5.17	40.3	—	10.05	2.02	1.72
90	9.74	—	3.34	16.85	—	1.70
120	16.22	—	3.44	23.20	1.20	1.89
150	20.86	35.2	3.35	27.65	1.10	1.82

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF MONOMER AND INITIATOR ON VISCOSITY AVERAGE MOLECULAR WEIGHTS (\bar{M}_v) OF THE POLYMERS, WHEN INJECTED LATE IN A RUN*

Run	[KPS] × 10 ³ mol dm ³	[M] mol dm ³	$\bar{M}_v \times 10^{-5}$ at different conversion			
			10%	20%	30%	40%
A	1.0	[AN] = 0.25	1.00	1.20	—	—
B	1.0	[AN] = 0.45	3.03	3.30	3.36	3.00
C	1.0		2.60	3.20	3.24	3.07
D	2.0	[AN] = 0.45	2.16	2.36	2.60	2.50
E		[AN] = 0.45	—	2.95	3.26	3.20
F	5.0	[MAN] = 0.24	4.90	4.06	—	—
G	5.0	[MAN] = 0.36	6.84	7.20	7.32	—
H	5.0		6.00	6.90	7.00	—
I	7.5	[MAN] = 0.24	2.56	2.80	—	—
J		[MAN] = 0.24	—	4.58	—	—

*Runs A, B, D, F, G and I are the control runs. In run-C, extra amount of monomer (AN, 0.20 mol dm⁻³) injected at 3.2% conversion of run-A; in run-E extra amount of initiator (1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³) injected at 12.5% conversion of run-B; in run-H, extra amount of monomer (MAN, 0.12 mol dm⁻³) injected at 5.0% conversion of run-F; in run-J, extra amount of initiator (2.5 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³) injected in run-F at 5.0% conversion.

time-average rate (i.e. total yield/total time of reaction). It has been found that in a run, the molecular weight (\bar{M}_v) of the polymer goes parallel with the average rate of polymerization.

Table 2 shows the difference between methacrylonitrile and acrylonitrile during the aqueous polymerizations. The effect of monomer injection, late in a run on the rate of polymerization is shown in Fig. 7. The rate of the aqueous polymerization is found to increase both in the case of AN and MAN. The data of Table 3 show that in the monomer injected experiments (late in a run) the \bar{M}_v of the polymer at a given conversion increases.

Fig. 8 shows the effect of initiator, injected late in a run on the rate of polymerization. Here, also, the rate is found to increase. However, no measurable change in \bar{M}_v of the polymers at a given conversion has been observed in the initiator injected experiments late in a run (Table 3). Fig. 9 shows the effect of injection (late in a run) of initiator and monomer on the molecular weight distribution of the polymer. The injection of extra initiator and monomer increases the dispersity of the polymer. Table 4 shows the particle size distribution in a latex solution.

The following mechanism has been suggested^{1,2} to explain the results of the thermal decomposition of persulphate in aqueous solution in the presence

Fig. 7. Effect of additional quantity of monomer when injected late in a run : (A) [AN] = 0.25 mol dm⁻³, [KPS] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³; (B) [AN] = 0.45 mol dm⁻³, [KPS] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³; (C) 0.20 mol dm⁻³, AN injected in the control run (A) after 1 h, i.e. about 3.2% conversion. Arrow indicates the injection point of additional quantity of monomer.

of monomer (methacrylonitrile, acrylonitrile) :

TABLE 4—PARTICLE SIZE DISTRIBUTION USING INSTRUMENT
 SELECTED DIAMETER RANGE

Latex solution prepared using recipe : [MAN] = 0.30 mol dm⁻³
 [KPS] = 7.5 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [NALS] = 1.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³, time of
 reaction = 190 min, conversion = 23%

Method : Direct calculation, Times 4, Interval 1 s

Range number	Particle diameter range (μm)	Volume% within range	Cumulative %
1	36.10–19.40	0	0
2	19.40–12.30	0	0
3	12.30–8.45	4.4	4.4
4	8.45–6.06	8.6	13.0
5	6.06–4.49	14.2	27.2
6	4.49–3.42	16.1	43.3
7	3.42–2.66	17.7	60.9
8	2.66–2.11	11.7	72.6
9	2.11–1.70	7.0	79.6
10	1.70–1.39	3.9	83.5
11	1.39–1.15	2.1	85.6
12	1.15–0.97	1.8	87.4
13	0.97–0.82	2.3	89.7
14	0.82–0.71	2.8	92.6
15	0.71–0.62	2.8	95.4
16	0.62–0.55	0	95.4
17	0.55–0.25	3.8	99.2
18	0.25	0.8	100

all in the aqueous phase.

in water, in the particle and also at the particle-water interface;

at the particle-water interface and $j = 1$ to 10;

at the particle-water interface;

in the water phase.

at the particle-water interface;

Fig. 8. Effect of initiator on conversion when injected late in a run : (A) [AN] = 0.30 mol dm⁻³, [KPS] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³; (B) [AN] = 0.30 mol dm⁻³, [KPS] = 2.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³; (C) extra amount of initiator (1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³) injected in the control run (A), after 1 h, i.e. at about 5.5% conversion. Arrow indicates the point of injection.

in water

in the latex particles or between two active particles if they coagulate, $i = 1$ to any value say 1000 or more. In this reaction scheme, $(M_j^*)_w$ are water-soluble monomeric or oligomeric free radicals, $j = 1$ to 10, according to Dainton *et al.*³; $(M_i)_p$ are radicals present in the latex particles⁴ which may be water-soluble or water-insoluble (when $i > 10$); if $i = j$, then M_j^* and M_i^* radicals are the same, it is assumed that M_i^* and R^* radicals are indistinguishable with respect to suggested chemical reactions; k_p and k_t are assumed to be independent of polymer chain-length^{5,6}. From the proposed reaction model, the rate of initiation

Fig. 9. Effects of extra amount of initiator and monomer injection (late in a run) on the molecular weight distribution : (sample A) $[MAN] = 0.30 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[KPS] = 5.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; (sample B) $[MAN] = 0.30 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[KPS] = 7.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; (sample C) prepared by adding extra amount of initiator ($2.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) late in a run (after 1 h) with the initial $[KPS]$ as $5.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; (sample D) prepared by adding extra amount of MAN (0.10 mol dm^{-3}) late in a run (after 1 h) with initial $[MAN]$ as 0.20 mol dm^{-3} ; time allowed for the polymerization = 165 min, temp. = $50 \pm 0.2^\circ$.

(R_i) in the aqueous phase and the total rate of termination (R_t) in the aqueous and latex phases are given by

$$R_i = \{2k_1 + 2k_5 [M]_w + k_{10} [M_i^*]_w\} [S_2O_8^{2-}] V_w \quad (14)$$

$$\text{and } R_t = 2k_{tp} [M_i^*]_p^2 V_p + 2 k_{tw} [M_i^*]_w^2 V_w \quad (15)$$

where V_w and V_p are the volume fractions of the water phase and of the polymer phase respectively, and $V_w + V_p = 1.0$. The estimated^{1,2} values of k_5 ($1.05 \times 10^{-5} - 1.70 \times 10^{-5} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$), k_{10} ($1.14 \times 10^3 - 5.08 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$) and $[M_i^*]_w$ ($\approx 10^{-9} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$), show that the initiation due to reaction (10) is negligible compared to those due to reactions (1) and (5) together at a given concentration of persulphate and of monomer. Hence neglecting reaction (10) in equation (14), we get under the steady state,

$$[M_i^*]_w = \frac{\{k_1 + k_5 [M]_w\}^{0.05} [S_2O_8^{2-}]^{0.5} V_w^{0.5}}{\{k_{tp} \beta^2 V_p + k_{tw} V_w\}^{0.5}} \quad (16)$$

where $\beta = [M_i^*]_p / [M_i^*]_w$ and have values as high as 1000 or more⁴.

We assume⁷ $[M_i^*]_p / [M_i^*]_w = [M]_p / [M]_w = \alpha$, where α is the distribution coefficient of monomer between the polymer phase and the aqueous phase under the experimental conditions. If $j = 1$, the above relation is not far from being true, since M_i^* and M have probably the same solubility in water. The steady-state rate of polymerization (R_p) is given by

$$R_p = k_p [M]_w (V_w + \beta \alpha V_p)$$

$$\left\{ \frac{(k_1 + k_5 [M]_w)^{0.5} [S_2O_8^{2-}]^{0.5} V_w^{0.5}}{(k_{tp} \beta^2 V_p + k_{tw} V_w)^{0.5}} \right\} \quad (17)$$

α has been measured experimentally by the bromometric estimation of the monomer present in the aqueous phase containing a known amount of polymer and of monomer, after keeping the solution at 50° in an inert atmosphere of nitrogen for 24 h to attain the equilibrium. The average value of α at 50° has been found to be 1.8 ± 0.2 for MAN and 0.5 ± 0.2 for AN. Under our experimental conditions, $V_w \gg V_p$, the equation (17) becomes simplified if we consider the following two extreme cases.

Case-I : When the aqueous phase polymerizations and terminations are more important compared to the corresponding reactions in the polymer phase, then the steady-state of polymerization at zero time or zero conversion may be written as

$$(R_p)_{t=0} = k_p k_{tw}^{-0.5} [M]_w \{k_1 + k_5 [M]_w\}^{0.5} [S_2O_8^{2-}]^{0.5} V_w \quad (18)$$

Squaring equation (18), and taking $V_w = 1.0$ at zero conversion, we get

$$\frac{(R_p)_{t=0}^2}{[M]_w^2} = \left\{ \frac{k_p^2}{k_{tw}} \right\} \{k_1 + k_5 [M]_w\} [S_2O_8^{2-}] \quad (19)$$

The plot of the left-hand-side of equation (19) against $[S_2O_8^{2-}]$ at a given concentration of monomer is a straight-line passing through the origin. From the slope of the line, k_{tw} can be estimated. Taking k_1 as $1.71 \times 10^{-6} \text{ s}^{-1}$, k_5 for

MAN¹ as $1.05 \times 10^{-5} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, k_p for MAN as $26 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ from literature⁸, k_5 for AN² as $1.70 \times 10^{-5} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and k_p for AN³ as $6.22 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, the estimated value of k_{tw} has been found to be $(2.00 \pm 0.70) \times 10^5 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for MAN and $(5.60 \pm 0.40) \times 10^{10}$ for AN.

Case-II : When the polymerization occurs mainly in the monomer-adsorbed PMAN or PAN latex particles as postulated by the Smith-Ewart or Medvedev theory⁵ and the aqueous phase termination is negligible, then we get

$$R_p = k_p [M]_w (V_w + \alpha \beta V_p) \cdot \frac{(k_1 + k_5 [M]_w)^{0.5} V_w^{0.5} [S_2O_8^{2-}]^{0.5}}{\beta (k_{tp} V_p)^{0.5}} \quad (20)$$

Since $\beta = [M_i]_p / [M_i]_w = 1000$ or more, then $(\alpha \beta V_p) > V_w$ and so

$$R_p = k_p [M]_w \alpha V_p^{0.5} k_{tp}^{-0.5} \{k_1 + k_5 [M]_w\}^{0.5} V_w^{0.5} [S_2O_8^{2-}]^{0.5}$$

or,
$$\frac{R_p}{(k_1 + k_5 [M]_w)^{0.5} [M]_w} = k_p \alpha k_{tp}^{-0.5} [S_2O_8^{2-}]^{0.5} (V_p V_w)^{0.5} \quad (21)$$

The plot of the left-hand-side of equation (21) against $(V_p V_w)^{0.5}$ at constant initiator concentration and at various concentrations of monomer is a straight-line passing through the origin.

From the slope of the line we get k_{tp} of AN = $(2.6 \pm 0.6) \times 10^7 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 50° taking $\alpha = 0.5$, and k_{tp} of MAN = $(1.90 \pm 0.50) \times 10^2 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 50° taking $\alpha = 1.8$.

The results suggest that the aqueous polymerization of MAN and AN initially takes place entirely in the aqueous phase; but with the progress of the polymerization reactions, the loci of the polymerization would gradually shift into the monomer adsorbed poly-MAN or poly-AN latex particles, and the polymerization would continue in both the phases. Chain initiation occurs in the aqueous phase by the primary free radical

(SO₄^{•-}) and also by the interaction of the monomer with the persulphate ions.

Under the identical condition, it is seen (Table 2) that the rate of the aqueous polymerization is higher in the AN-KPS system than that in the MAN-KPS system. This is probably due to the higher value of the propagation constant (k_p) of AN, compared to that of MAN. It has also been seen that the values of k_5 , k_{10} , k_{tw} and k_{tp} for the acrylonitrile monomer are higher than the counterpart rate constants of the methacrylonitrile monomer. Moreover, the higher solubility in water of AN compared to MAN is also responsible for the increased rate of the aqueous polymerization of AN compared to MAN.

Both in the case of MAN and AN the injection of extra amount of initiator late in a run increases the rate of aqueous polymerization but has no measurable effect on the viscosity average molecular weight (\bar{M}_v) of the polymer whereas the addition of extra amount of monomer late in a run increases both the rate of polymerization and the viscosity average molecular weight of the polymer. The addition of extra amount of monomer late in a run, would increase the monomer concentration in the latex particles and so the rate of polymerization would increase. Since \bar{M}_w / \bar{M}_n (i.e. dispersity) increases after the injection of extra amount of initiator and monomer late in a run (Fig. 9), it suggests that the new particles have been produced as a result of which frequency of radical capture by the particles was decreased leading to increase in the dispersity or molecular weights of the polymer.

Experimental

Polymerizations of MAN and AN were studied gravimetrically in a 1-litre round bottom pyrex flask fitted with a Hg seal stirrer and side-tubes for passing nitrogen and extracting solutions under nitrogen pressure for analysis. The details of the experimental procedure, purification and processing of monomer, molecular weight determination, etc., have been reported elsewhere^{1,2}. The polymerizations of both the monomers were studied within their solubility regions [i.e. < 2.8% (w/w) in case on MAN and < 8.5 (w/w) in case of

AN] at 50° in an atmosphere of nitrogen, and in order to avoid complications during polymerizations, no buffer solution was used. The pH of the medium was always above 3.5 when the H⁺ catalysed decomposition of persulphate ions is not significant⁹. The polymer formed was a stable colloid. The colloidal stability (C.S.) of the latex solution was measured¹⁰ by titrating a known volume of the latex solution with a standard (0.04 or 0.02 M) MgSO₄ solution. Molecular weight of the polymers was estimated by viscosity method.

The intrinsic viscosity (η) was measured in dimethylformamide (DMF) at 30° and the specific viscosity of the polymer solutions was determined in the concentration range of 0.1 to 0.30 g/100 cm³. The viscosity average molecular weights \bar{M}_v of the polymers are given by⁸

$$[\eta] = K \times \bar{M}_v^a$$

where $K = 306 \times 10^{-3} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ g}^{-1}$, $a = 0.503$ for poly-MAN and $K = 33.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ g}^{-1}$, $a = 0.72$ for poly-AN.

The weight-average molecular weight (\bar{M}_w), number average molecular weight (\bar{M}_n), molecular weight distribution and dispersity for the polymer samples were measured by GPC 200 (Waters, USA) and using *N,N*-dimethylformamide as the mobile phase. The particle size distribution of the latex solution was determined by SALD-1000 laser diffraction particles size analyzer (M/s. Chemito, India).

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